

Romantics and their Contribution to English Literature

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Abstract: This paper aims to highlight romantics and what they had contributed to English Literature. The focus will be on William Wordsworth, Samuel Taylor Coleridge, Lord Byron, John Keats, Percy Bysshe Shelley and some others. Their theories for literature and their views about poetry will be examined and analyzed. Furthermore, some of the poems of every writer will be analyzed as first hand sources to prove the point with regard to romanticism in English Literature. Poetry, its language, its subject will be focus and whom it is addressed will be given stress. Romanticism focused on imagination, lyrical quality, simple language, rural subject matter, nature, justice, freedom, equality and harmony with nature. All these things will be discussed and scrutinized.

Keywords: Romanticism, imagination, lyric, nature and language etc.

Objectives:

To analyze how romantics revolutionized literature, especially English poetry,

To explain what was the contribution of romantics in terms of poetry and their theories.

Methodology of Research

Researcher has focused on both primary and secondary sources so that objectives of this paper can be satisfied. Research design is purely descriptive, explanatory, analytical and comparative in its description. Collection of data has been done via internet. Focus will be on close textual reading, analysis and interpretation.

Introduction

“Romanticism, attitude or intellectual orientation that characterized many works of literature, painting, music, architecture, criticism, and historiography in Western civilization over a period from the late 18th to the mid-19th century. Romanticism can be seen as a rejection of the precepts of order, calm, harmony, balance, idealization, and rationality that typified Classicism in general and late 18th-century Neoclassicism in particular. It was also to some extent a reaction against the Enlightenment and against 18th-century rationalism and physical materialism in general. Romanticism emphasized the individual, the subjective, the irrational, the imaginative, the personal, the spontaneous, the emotional, the visionary, and the transcendental.”(<https://www.britannica.com/> Retrieved on 13/12/2025 at 3:36 pm)

Though this movement affected different fields but its effect can be perceived chiefly on English literature. It altogether changed the stance, manner and matter of English poetry. Though its seeds were sown in 1770s with gothic but it literally began in 1798 with the publication of *Lyrical Ballads* which was jointly written and brought forth by William Wordsworth and Samuel Taylor Coleridge. This manuscript was republished several times and it reacted against the principles of classical and neoclassical traditions. It challenged the rules laid down for poetry by the earlier writers and started a new era in English literature which continued to 1830s fully but it lost its momentum later. Wordsworth and Coleridge were its main exponents but Keats, Byron and Shelley along with others cannot be ignored. Its subject matter was very general; its aim was to reach general public. It laid down new rules and laws for poetry and literature and thus revolutionized literature. Nature and beauty got permanent place in this kind of literature.

Review of Literature, Analysis and Discussion

William Wordsworth

“He rejects the language used in the city and the court and prefers the language used in the field and farms. He dismisses the important feature of neoclassical poetry that is poetic diction and personification of abstract ideas, because they are artificial. On contrary he says a good poetry new “spontaneous overflow of powerful feelings”....Poetry must be a truthful representation of nature. He defined poetry as “the spontaneous overflow of powerful feelings”.....Poet has actual since experience that excites is emotion. Poet collects the previous or emotional experiences he had. The emotions recollected in the first and second stage are transferred to the

mind. The Mind transformer is emotions into Idea or thought to be expressed in the poem. The composition of poem begins at this stage.”

(<https://art810943965.wordpress.com/> Retrieved on 14/12/2025 at 3:59 pm)

William Wordsworth was a simple man with abundant love for nature. He is the father of this movement. It is he who challenged the norms of old poetry and set new laws both for a poet and poetry. Nature has highest place in art in his opinion and he simplified poetry and unshackled it from rigorous chains of strict rules. For him poetry is when emotions overflow the mind and at peace one is able create verse. Creation of poetry involves observation, emotion, recollection, contemplation, and then imaginative excitement, leading to the poem. It is poet who creates poetry. Poetry represents nature. Language of poetry is the common speech of men in action. Its subject is general man. The poet is a man speaking to men, sharing genuine emotional experiences to improve readers' understanding and capacity for feeling. To give pleasure by increasing understanding and refining emotions, not just to instruct is the function of poetry for this great poet of romantic era. Unlike Greeks, classical and neo-classical writers he believes poet is a man speaking to men and poet is not superior but only aim of poet is to describe men and nature. His poetry is the true picture of nature, he is a nature lover and we can also call him environmentalist. He wanted man to have close affinity with nature. He never allowed for destruction of nature.

“The world is too much with us; late and soon/Getting and spending, we lay waste our powers;/Little we see in Nature that is ours;/We have given our hearts away, a sordid boon”(<https://www.poetryfoundation.org/> Retrieved on 15/12/2025 at 4:54 pm)! He says that man has lost his touch with nature because materialism has eaten him. Man became so much commercial that he wastes his life in amassing wealth and spending it back. He has not only lost

himself but he has lost peace as well. By abandoning nature man has gained nothing but worst things.

There was a time when meadow, grove, and stream,

The earth, and every common sight,

To me did seem

Apparelled in celestial light,

The glory and the freshness of a dream.

It is not now as it hath been of yore;—

Turn wheresoever's I may,

By night or day

The things which I have seen I now can see no more.”

(<https://www.poetryfoundation.org/> retrieved on 15/12/2025 at 5:12 pm)

Again here the poet by speaking to himself, says that nature is not same now. Earlier it was a thing divine, I was enjoying it then but what has happened now. The interest is gone. After he returned from France, he can see the changes in himself as well. But later on in the poem he says how much he has missed the nature and how much he has loved it and is still in love. For him, nature is home. It is the solace, it provides wisdom and it is combination of man, environment and God. He can perceive god in every object of nature.

In “Daffodils” he makes it clear that even smallest piece of nature can bring joy. “I wandered lonely as a cloud/That floats on high o'er vales and hills,/When all at once I saw a crowd,/A host, of golden daffodils”(<https://www.poetryfoundation.org/> retrieved on 15/12/2025 at 6:00 pm). There is the sight of pure enjoyment and pure delight in it. There is a call back to nature though only implied not suggested. “For oft, when on my couch I lie/In vacant or in

pensive mood,/They flash upon that inward eye/Which is the bliss of solitude;”(https://www.poetryfoundation.org/ retrieved on 15/12/2025 at 6:00 pm).

These four lines are his suggestion that by enjoying and observing nature man can attain bliss and such an event with nature can be a receptacle for the creation of poetry when a man is peaceful in pensive mood all these things can be brought back and one can create poetry. So nature is the source of the poetry.

William Wordsworth transformed the concept of poetry in English. He focused on nature, its beauty and delight, life of a common man, and straightforward speech. His poetry is intensely lyrical with love for nature at its core.

Samuel Taylor Coleridge

Samuel Taylor Coleridge was a companion poet of Wordsworth, though they contributed for *Lyrical Ballads* but his focus was on imagination, fancy and supernatural.

“In Chapter XIII of *Biographia Literaria*, Coleridge writes: “The imagination then I consider either as primary, or secondary”. According to Coleridge, Imagination has two forms; primary and secondary. Primary imagination is merely the power of receiving impressions of the external world through the senses, the power of perceiving the objects of sense, both in their parts and as a whole. It is a spontaneous act of the mind; the human mind receives impressions and sensations from the outside world, unconsciously and involuntarily, imposes some sort of order on those impressions, reduces them to shape and size, so that the mind is able to form a clear image of the outside world. In this way clear and coherent

perception becomes possible. The primary imagination is universal, it is possessed by all. The secondary imagination may be possessed by others also, but it is the peculiar and typical trait of the artist. It is the secondary imagination which makes artistic creation possible. Secondary imagination is more active and conscious; it requires an effort of the will, volition and conscious effort. It works upon its raw material that is the sensations and impressions supplied to it by the primary imagination.” (<https://snim.in/> retrieved on 16/12/2025 at 6:30 pm)

Coleridge puts more emphasis on Secondary Imagination and says it is active agent that helps to create poetry from the sources that has been received by Primary Imagination.

“Fancy is not a creative power at all. It only combines what it perceives into beautiful shapes, but like the imagination it does not fuse and unify. The difference between the two is the same as the difference between a mechanical mixture and a chemical compound. In a mechanical mixture a number of ingredients are brought together. They are mixed up, but they do not lose their individual properties. In a chemical compound, the different ingredients combine to form something new. The different ingredients no longer exist as separate identities. They lose their respective properties and fuse together to create something new and entirely different. A compound is an act of creation; while a mixture is merely a bringing together of a number of separate elements.”(<https://snim.in/> retrieved on 16/12/2025 at 6:30 pm).

The above quote makes it clear that fancy is inferior to imagination. It is also a receptacle and can receive and combine but new forms are created with the help of imagination rather than fancy.

Down to a sunless sea.

So twice five miles of fertile ground

With walls and towers were girdled round;

And there were gardens bright with sinuous rills,

Where blossomed many an incense-bearing tree;

And here were forests ancient as the hills,

Enfolding sunny spots of greenery. (poetryfoundation.org/ retrieved on 18/12/2025 at 6:30 pm)

Coleridge is very clear when he describes a place it seems that something dreamy has been built there. Trees, gardens, flowers and their fragrance take reader to some unknown land with luring quality. He is able to create what one can perceive in a dream. “Water, water, everywhere,/And all the boards did shrink;/Water, water, everywhere,/Nor any drop to drink”(poetryfoundation.org/ retrieved on 18/12/2025 at 6:30 pm). In these lines we are taken into the sea and feel a very dreadful atmosphere as can be perceived in the lines. Imagination has been given a high role and poet himself also feels blissful and he enjoys the place. “The very deep did rot: O Christ!/That ever this should be!/Yea, slimy things did crawl with legs/Upon the slimy sea” poetryfoundation.org/ retrieved on 18/12/2025 at 8:30 pm).

“And some in dreams assurèd were/Of the Spirit that plagued us so;/Nine fathom deep he had followed us/From the land of mist and snow” (https://www.poetryfoundation.org/ retrieved on 18/12/2025 at 8:50 pm). Coleridge has power to create things which are very difficult to

believe. He gives accurate description of things very clearly. The colours he used create sensation in our minds, it is clear that imagism has been used to its full quality. Words are apt when poet uses them and meaning is clearly mentioned and clarified.

For Coleridge the function of a poem is to please the readers. He suggests that all the elements of poem must work together as an organic whole and provide the pleasing effect. All these elements like meter, rhyme, content etc. must play their part in deriving the pleasure. A poet according to Coleridge must stir the imagination of the readers and in such a way must reveal some deeper truth. Poet must first understand the world himself and he must act like a philosopher. He is not only to please but to reveal deeper and concealed truths. He must create knowledge beyond the logic. The poet balances contradictory (e.g., universal/real, idea/image, novelty/acquaintance) to create philosophical connotation.

Percy Bysshe Shelley

Major contribution of romantic poet, Percy Bysshe Shelley to English Poetry includes his towering emotional approach, farsighted issues of life like emancipation, gorgeousness, and imagination, inventive use of scenery's as figure of speeches, and commanding political rhyme that championed reformation. It solidified his place among the major romantics. He challenged tyranny and was a best revolutionary in his spirit. His poetry is full of radical thinking and philosophy of life. There is much beauty and ideology that speaks for freedom and equality. Shelley demonstrated romantic ideals, and focused on liberty, uniqueness, power of nature, and the sublimity, frequently bearing in mind nature as a medium to intellectual exquisiteness and truth. "Thou, from whose unseen presence the leaves dead/As thus with thee in prayer in my sore need./Oh, lift me as a wave, a leaf, a cloud!/I fall upon the thorns of life! I bleed"(https://www.poetryfoundation.org/retrieved_on_19/12/2025_at_2:00 pm). This is how

power of nature is described by using the symbol of wind and he also demands freedom in a way symbolically. He challenged the politics and religion. He shows mastery in use of techniques like meter forms of poetry.

Shelley's own understanding marks the poet as a prophet, not a man dispensing forecasts but a person who participates in the eternal, and the infinite. He goes on to place poetry in the column of divine and organic process. A poem is the very image of life expressed in its eternal truth. The task of poets then is to interpret and present the poem; Shelley's metaphor here explicates: "oetry is a mirror which makes beautiful of what seems distorted.

"Shelley argued for the significance of imagination, seeing it as a creative force that shapes insight, connects humankind, and drives societal transformation. He used powerful symbols (the Wind, the *Skylark*, the Prometheus Unbound myth) to discover compound thoughts about annihilation, formation, beauty, and the human spirits potential."
(<https://www.poetryfoundation.org/retrieved on 19/12/2025> at 2:31pm)

Poetry to him is an expression of imagination; it is higher form of thought and reason. It is creative process which reveals universal forms.

"From reason and imagination, man may recognize beauty, and it is through beauty that civilization comes. Language, Shelley contends, shows humanity's impulse toward order and harmony, which leads to an appreciation of unity and beauty. Those in "excess" of language are the poets, whose task it is to impart the pleasures of their experience and observations into poems. Shelley argues that civilization advances and thrives with the help of poetry."
(<https://www.poetryfoundation.org/retrieved on 19/12/2025> at 2:51pm)

A poem is the picture of life articulated in its everlasting reality, capturing the essence of human existence. It records the best and happiest moments of the happiest and best minds. Verse is the maximum gadget of ethical good, development, compassion, justice, and liberty. It motivates with the help of loveliness and emotion, rather than instructing direct lessons.

Poets form society's principles and thoughts, and affect the laws and civilization ultimately. They are interpreters of the celestial and the infinite, connecting the temporal world with eternal truths. They produce new opinions and events, and are the inventors of verbal communication, religious conviction, and art. Poets are reflection of the enormous shadows which futurity casts upon the present. They reveal what others cannot see. They are conduit for an unapprehended stimulation moved by forces beyond themselves, like trumpets which sing to battle, and feel not what they inspire. Poets to Shelley occupy highest place. "Poets are the unacknowledged legislators of the world"(https://www.poetryfoundation.org/retrieved_on_19/12/2025 at 2:51pm). They are the makers of laws that people follow knowingly and unknowingly. They do not teach but express and their views provide pleasure. Poets are prophets and they reveal what a common man cannot perceive.

"But poets, or those who imagine and express this indestructible order, are not only the authors of language and of music, of the dance, and architecture, and statuary, and painting: they are the institutors of laws, and the founders of civil society, and the inventors of the arts of life, and the teachers, who draw into a certain propinquity with the beautiful and the true that partial apprehension of the agencies of the invisible world which is called religion."
https://www.poetryfoundation.org/retrieved_on_19/12/2025 at 2:51pm)

Poets for him were founders of societies and laws. He gave them the position of prophets. His contribution is enormous thought not bulky in amount but in content and connotation. Like other romantics he was a rebel and tried to transform the world of poetry and human world. All his writing has the element of rebellion and a wish for freedom, justice, equality and harmony.

John Keats

According to John Keats, a bard is a chameleon who lacks set identity. He is able to experience the whole thing from ape to Plato. He embodies sympathy and Negative Capability to reside in doubt, while verse itself is a dream-like escape. It is a revelatory fusion of truth and beauty, surprising by fine excess, and a way to make life's intense, fleeting moments enduring through imagination, not a mere teaching. Poet is an interpreter of life for Keats.

Poetry is a gorgeous world of dream to break away from suffering. It reveals intuitions about the cosmos rather than instructing. Its ultimate aim is the realization of beauty, which symbolizes reality, creating enduring art from transitory life. “Beauty is truth, truth beauty,—that is all/Ye know on earth, and all ye need to know” (<https://www.poetryfoundation.org/> retrieved on 19/12/2025 at 3:22pm). Among all the romantics Keats was the greatest lover of beauty. He had shown how man can escape the world of suffering but in general man has to be grounded in truth. He wanted the nightingale to take him into his world but was brought back by the realization. Same way Robert Frost wanted to escape the world by mounting a Birch Tree but he also was brought back by realization of life.

Keats wanted to make life permanent with the help of art. The example of which can be seen in “Ode on a Grecian Urn”. “Bold Lover, never, never canst thou kiss,/Though winning near the goal yet, do not grieve;/She cannot fade, though thou hast not thy bliss,/Forever wilt

thou love, and she be fair” ([https://www.poetryfoundation.org/retrieved on 19/12/2025](https://www.poetryfoundation.org/retrieved%20on%2019/12/2025) at 4:pm)! Here he shows picture of faithful couple who cannot reach each other but their longing for each other is eternal. Eternal love is possible only in art. Poetry should surprise with fine excess, make the reader feel his/her own highest thoughts are being expressed. It must evoke intense emotion and imagination.

Keats believed in beauty that which appeals to the senses, examples is his odes. He was a master of ode style. He gave the concept of Negative Capability. His work beautifully intertwines pleasure and pain, reality and imagination, and mortality with the immortal, finding beauty in conflict such as “La Belle Dame sans Merci”. Keats was a supreme lyricist, using intricate rhyme, rhythm, and sound devices to create melodious and memorable verses. He blends elements of Greek mythology with his poetry which labeled him as a Hellenist and the concept was given the name of Hellenism.

Result and Findings

Romanticism reformed English poetry and freed it from strict rules and brought changes in thinking.

They argued for easy language, common man as the subject of the poetry and poet must talk to common man.

Imagination plays prominent role in creative process of poetry along with fancy, though fancy is only a receptacle.

Beauty and nature are important themes in poetry of romantics.

Poetry is the expression of personal emotions.

Liberty, equality, freedom of speech, justice and brother must be promoted.

Man must develop a strong bond with nature and Wordsworth found abundant peace in it.

Romanticism was all humanism.

Conclusion

Romanticism was a movement that changed the route of English poetry. All the romantics were rebels and they brought revolution not only in poetry but in life and literature of English. Most prominent romantics were Wordsworth, Coleridge, Shelley Keats and Byron. This form of poetry was humanistic in design. Poets argued for freedom, equality, justice and brotherhood. Poetry for them was expression of life and it was freed from its strict rules. They loved and beatified art and nature, most of their verse was personal.

References

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